

**STAFF WORKING CONDITIONS AND APPRAISAL AS CORRELATES OF EDUCATIONAL
MANAGEMENT UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOME IN UNIVERSITIES IN
NORTH-CENTRAL AND NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA**

BAKARI, Halima Betso¹, BADAU, Kabiru Mohammed², & OLOWOSELU, Abdulrasheed³

¹Federal Inland Revenue Service, Yola MSTO, Nigeria

² & ³Department of Educational Foundation, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: betsohalima@gmail.com, +2347063313920

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14729444>

ABSTRACT

This study determined how staff working conditions and appraisal are correlates of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The study adopted correlational research design, with three research questions and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study was 1,388 staff and students in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and Planning programme in the study area. The sample of the study was 341 respondents (i.e., 105 academic staff and 236 students), which was selected using multistage sampling technique. A self-constructed questionnaire titled: "Staff Working Conditions and Appraisal Questionnaire (SWCAQ)" plus pro-forma titled: Educational Management Final Year Students' CGPA were used as the instruments for data collection. The instruments were validated and pilot tested with Cronbach Alpha statistic showing a reliability co-efficient of 0.84 for HRMPQ. The data collected were analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions; while Simple Linear and Multiple Regression Analyses were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the hypotheses revealed that there is a significant correlation between staff working condition, staff appraisal and students' academic achievement. Collectively, the findings showed that there is a significant correlation between staff working conditions, staff appraisal and students' learning outcome. Hence, the study concluded that staff working conditions and staff appraisal are significant correlates of students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that universities' administrators should improve staff working conditions, such as providing adequate facilities, teaching resources, and a supportive work environment, which positively influence students' learning outcome.

Keywords: Staff Working Conditions, Staff Appraisal, Student Learning Outcome, Student Academic Achievement, Educational Management

INTRODUCTION

Education is generally referred to as any positive change of behaviour, attitude, experience that has effect on mind, character or physical appearance of the individual and it is a continuous process which goes on throughout one's life. Education is a process of transmitting knowledge and skills to younger generation through schools, colleges, universities and other mass media like radio, film, television, magazines and newspapers (Usman, 2015). In Nigeria, the Federal Government through its policy on education divide the educational systems into Basic Education (pre-primary, primary and junior

secondary school), Post Basic Education and Tertiary Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013). Tertiary education, is the level of education that provides students with instruction in school administration and planning, as well as educational management. Hence, educational management students must be well equipped in terms of their learning outcomes to attain these goals.

Learning outcomes according to Korde (2021) refers to what learners should be able to do/perform as a result of some learning experience achieved in a given course of study. It is also the statement of the knowledge, attitude and abilities individual students should possess and can demonstrate upon the completion of a learning experience. Teaching students to read, write and calculate is often considered the primary purpose of formal education, but students' regular attendance and attention in school also help to guarantee students' learning outcome (Aneth, 2017). The environment, content and processes that learners encounter in school lead to diverse results, some intended and others unintended. Quality learner outcomes are intentional, expected effects of the educational system. It includes what students know and can do, as well as the attitudes and expectations they have for themselves and their societies (Bakari & Bambi, 2021). Hence, the quality of learning outcomes includes the ability of students to demonstrate sound knowledge, values and skills in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning, which are shown by the marks/grades obtained in examinations and their attitude upon graduation. In the context of this study, students' learning outcome was limited to students' level of academic achievement in educational management courses at universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

In most universities, Bakari and Bambi (2021) argued that many factors constitute to the non-attainment of high students' learning outcome, as most institutions' resources are ill-equipped while some management personnel do not manage effectively the few available resources for improving students' learning outcome. Other factors that constitute low students' learning outcome, according to Aneth (2017) include funding, students' readiness to learn, teacher quality, teacher motivation, available facilities, academic content and the overall learning environment. In addition, Aithal and Suresh (2016) suggested quality of teaching, students support services, students' mental health and well-being, curricula and skills gap. Majority of these factors could be classified as resources. Resources used in the educational setting for the purpose of achieving educational goals are called educational resource and majorly include material, financial and human resources. The chief among these resources is the human resource. A university's human resource include the academic and non-academic staffs that have been employed by the institution to help in the teaching and learning process. These staff take decisions, which provide the knowledge, energy and the co-operation through which the university objectives, which include quality students' learning outcome could be achieved. Hence, staff effective management through staff working conditions and appraisals are essential to the realisation of quality students' learning outcome.

Staff working condition generally refers to work environment and all circumstance in existence that can affect educators in schools. This include, hours spent on job, physical aspects, rights that are legal, assigning of responsibility and students' development. In another vein, working conditions come into play by the relationship of teachers with their schools' culture and this includes physical as well as psychological working conditions (Keston, 2015). In an ideal work environment, it is expected that good furniture (comfortable office tables, chairs, shelves, cupboard and file cabinets), beautiful and serene environments, neat and aesthetic office buildings are provided for workers. Unfortunately, the reverse is the case. It is not uncommon to see lecturers and other non-academic staff in the university sharing offices and some other office equipment through partitioning (Adeniji, Adelenia & Ogunbile, 2022). These do not only affect staff motivation but also staff commitment towards achieving students' learning outcome. Also, staff working condition include maintaining an appropriate student-

teacher ratio in the university. However, most class sizes in North-Central and North-East, Nigerian universities are too large, which often limit students' attention and interaction with lecturers (Bakari, 2019).

Staff performance appraisal according to Dinna and Michal (2015), is an aspect of human resource management that assesses the productivity or level of performance of individual employees. Performance appraisal is a working procedure that creates a system where school organizations recognize not only employees' level of efficiency, but also the areas where they need performance improvement, in order to provide for optimum use of their staff (Arimie & Orobosa, 2023). Also, performance appraisal gives feedback to employees on the positive and negative aspects of staff performance which are likely to affect students' learning outcome. Staff appraisal is very critical in enhancing academic staff performance in public universities since it could serve as a roadmap for assessing lecturers as well as the general performance of institutions towards achieving quality students' learning outcome. Thus, staff appraisal helps the institution to identify lecturers' areas of improvement in teaching, administrative function, communication and work performance.

From the foregoing, it could be conceived that staff working condition and appraisal in education plays a critical role in educational institutions by shaping the work environment, supporting staff development and ensuring the effective delivery of education. In the context of undergraduate educational management programmes in the study area, staff working condition and appraisal have the potential to significantly impact students' learning outcome either positively or negatively. Thus, there was a need to investigate and understand the specific correlation between human resource management and the learning outcomes of undergraduate educational management students especially in universities in the study area. Hence, it was in view of the aforementioned discussions that the researchers investigated the correlation between staff working condition, appraisal and students' learning outcome in educational management programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The current situation in educational management programmes across universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria reveals a troubling trend of poor students' learning outcome, characterized by low academic achievement. Despite efforts to enhance educational quality, the researchers observed that some students in educational management programmes in the study area continue to exhibit disengagement, lack of motivation, and underperformance in their academic pursuits. This persistent issue not only undermines the effectiveness of the educational management curriculum but also jeopardizes the future competence of graduates who are expected to lead and innovate in the educational sector.

The consequences of these poor learning outcomes are far-reaching. Graduates with low academic achievement and poor attitudes are less likely to excel in professional settings, diminishing ability to contribute effectively to the educational system. Moreover, the reputation of the institutions offering educational management programme suffers, potentially leading to a decrease in student enrolment and a lack of trust from stakeholders. The broader educational landscape is also affected, as poorly trained educational managers may propagate ineffective practices, further entrenching systemic issues within the sector. Addressing these challenges is critical to ensuring that the next generation of educational leaders is equipped with the skills, knowledge, and mindset needed to drive positive change.

In essence, the success or failure of educational management programmes in the study area hinges on the strategic implementation of HRM practices such as staff working conditions and appraisal that prioritize the well-being and professional growth of academic staff. However, there are no empirical evidence in the study area to support the relationship between HRM practices (staff working conditions and appraisal) and students' learning outcome.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study sought to determine the correlation between staff working conditions, staff appraisal and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study were to determine whether:

1. Staff working conditions is a correlate of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.
2. Staff appraisal is a correlate of educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In order to achieve the specific objectives of the study, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of staff working conditions in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of staff appraisal in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?
3. What is the mean score of educational management undergraduate students' cumulative grade points average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant correlation between staff working conditions and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant correlation between staff appraisal and educational management undergraduate students' learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical framework of this study was based on the Social Exchange Theory as postulated by George Homans in 1958 and Social Cognitive Theory propounded by psychologist Albert Bandura in 1986. According to Social Exchange Theory (SET), individuals engage in social interactions based on the calculation of costs and benefits. They seek to maximize rewards and minimize costs in their relationships. SET recognizes the importance of a supportive work environment in fostering positive exchange relationships. Universities can create a supportive work environment for lecturers by offering resources, facilities and administrative support necessary for effective teaching and research. Providing a collegial and collaborative atmosphere, opportunities for mentoring and networking and a fair and transparent promotion and tenure process can further enhance the exchange relationship.

The SCT, is a psychological framework that emphasizes the reciprocal interaction between personal factors, environmental influences and behaviour. SCT stated that individuals learn and develop through a process of observation, imitation and the cognitive processing of information. The relatedness of Social Cognitive Theory, as developed by Albert Bandura to the current study is because it provides insights students' learning outcome through observational learning, self-

efficacy, modelling teacher behaviour, self-regulation, feedback and reinforcement. SCT highlights the importance of observational learning in educational settings. Students can learn from observing others, such as teachers, peers, or even multimedia sources. In addition, lecturers serve as important models for students and their behaviour can impact students' learning outcome.

Staff Working Condition and Students' Learning Outcome

Working condition as a concept is a generic and complex one. It generally includes things like scheduling for rest breaks, salary and the physical and mental demands of the activities that employees must complete. Hence, Adeniji, Adelena and Ogunbile (2022) investigated if staff work conditions is a correlate with job commitment in Ogun State-Owned Universities, Nigeria. Findings revealed the sampled workers have a high level of job commitment ($X = 3.14$), work in an adequate environment ($X = 2.93$) and that work conditions is a correlate of job commitment ($r = 270, p=0.000 < 0.05$) among university staff. Also, Kidanie (2022) study, which focused on measuring the effect of workplace environment factors on performance of Wollo University: the case of College of Business and Economics employees. The findings on the modelling of the employees' performance against the workplace environment factors showed at 5% significant level the multiple linear regression model was statistically significant (p-value 0.001). Akpomi, Tamuno-Omuna and Gbere (2021) examined the influence of working conditions on job performance of Business Education lecturers in Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. Findings from the study showed that, job security and promotion as at when due influences the job and students' performance of Business Education lecturers in Universities in Rivers State to a high extent.

Staff Performance Appraisal and Students' Learning Outcome

A performance appraisal system is a useful tool that can be used to raise the level of employee performance within an organisation. A study conducted by Muchai, Makokha and Namusonge (2018), recognised staff appraisal as a crucial component of administrative control procedures and human resources management. A structured system of reviewing and evaluating an individual's or a team's performance on a task is called a performance appraisal (PA) (Ulabor & Agelebe, 2022). Hence, Ulabor and Agelebe (2022) examined performance appraisal on organization performance of selected tertiary institutions in Osun State. Findings revealed that effective performance appraisal system affects employee's commitment ($\chi^2 = 75.004, p\text{-value} = .000$). Additionally, Rwothumio, Okaka, Kambaza and Kyomukama (2021) investigated the relationship between performance appraisal and teaching and research outputs of academic staff in selected public universities in Uganda. Results indicated that a moderate positive relationship existed between performance appraisal and academic staff teaching output in public universities and a moderately positive relationship existed between performance appraisal and academic staff research output. This therefore shows that a relationship exists between the variables. However, this is known in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlational research design. This study was carried out in North-Central and North-East Geopolitical Zones of Nigeria. The North Central Zone includes Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau States, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), where Nigeria's capital city, Abuja, is situated. On the other hand, the North-East Zone comprises of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe states. The population of the study was 1,388 respondents (210 academic staff and 1,178 final-year students) in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and Planning degree programme at public universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The sample size of this study was 341 respondents (105 academic staff and 236 final year students) in undergraduate Educational Management/Administration and

Planning degree programme of public universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria which represented 50% of the population of academic staff and 20% of the entire population of final year students (Gall, Gall & Borg, 2007). Therefore, the researchers used the multistage sampling technique (that comprised of cluster sampling, simple random, purposive, proportionate and convenience sampling techniques).

The instruments that were used for data collection in this study were a self-structured questionnaire and pro-forma. The self-structured questionnaire was titled: “Staff Working Conditions and Appraisal Questionnaire (SWCAQ)” while the pro-forma was titled: “Educational Management Final Year Students’ CGPA”. The research instruments were validated by four experts, three from the Department of Physical Sciences Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, while the fourth was from the Department of Educational Foundation, Taraba State University, Jalingo. The SWCAQ was subjected to reliability testing through the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which revealed an internal consistency of 0.84, that meant the instrument was reliable. The data were gathered through a letter of introduction and the aid of four research assistants. At the end of the data collection exercise, 324 (103 from staff and 221 from students) valid questionnaires were retrieved which amounts to 95% of the total questionnaires administered. Hence, mean, standard deviation and simple linear regression were used to analysed the data collected.

RESULTS

The results are presented in the order of research questions and hypotheses from Table 1 – 5. For the research questions, the keys represent: n = no of respondents, Std. Dev = Standard Deviation, HL = High Level, ML = Moderate Level and LL = Low Level.

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the level of staff working conditions in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Staff Working Conditions in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 103	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	The university has provided adequate classroom facilities for staff to carry out their job in the institution		3.52	1.45	HL
2.	Staff have access to the available equipment necessary for performing their tasks		3.22	1.34	ML
3.	The Head of Department often provides staff with sufficient information related to their work		3.06	1.30	ML
4.	There are enough possibilities in the faculty to receive teaching/administrative assistance from colleagues when necessary		3.74	1.28	HL
5.	The faculty environment is conducive enough to grant staff lone time to perform their duties		3.56	1.16	HL
6.	Research collaboration among colleagues has aided staff’s job effectiveness in your institution		3.68	1.29	HL
7.	There is regular maintenance of departmental building, which makes the vicinity conducive		3.11	1.20	ML
	Grand Mean		3.41		ML

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

From the above Table 1 shows that the staff working conditions in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria has a grand mean score of 3.41, which indicate a moderate level.

Research Question 2: What is the level of staff appraisal in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of Staff Appraisal in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	n = 103	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
8.	The university offers a transparent process for rating the productivity of its academic staff		3.54	1.39	HL
9.	The appraisal system in the university is actually focused on lecturers' job activities		3.90	1.44	HL
10.	University performance appraisal provides administrators with the chance to determine the training requirements for staff		4.10	1.45	HL
11.	In the university, performance appraisal gives lecturers the chance to advance their research publications		3.86	1.31	HL
12.	After appraisal, timely feedback on job performance is given to every staff		3.83	1.19	HL
13.	Lecturers' work performance has improved due to the university's performance appraisal system		3.59	1.42	HL
14.	Students' academic successes are occasionally used as the basis for appraisal		3.71	1.20	HL
Grand Mean			3.79		HL

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

From the above Table 2 shows that staff appraisal in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria has a grand mean score of 3.79, which indicate a high level.

Research Question 3: What is the mean score of educational management undergraduate students' cumulative grade points average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Mean Score of Educational Management Undergraduate Students' Cumulative Grade Points Average in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	Taraba State University EDM Final Year Students' CGPA	3.29	0.62	ML
2.	University of Abuja EDM Final Year Students' CGPA	3.13	0.48	ML
3.	Benue State University EDM Final Year Students' CGPA	3.64	0.93	ML
4.	Federal University, Kashere EDM Final Year Students' CGPA	3.23	0.71	ML
5.	Prince Abubakar Audu University, Kogi EDM Final Year Students' CGPA	2.78	0.56	ML
Grand Mean		3.21		ML

Source: Exams and Records Department of the University

The above table reveals a grand mean of 3.21. This means that students’ cumulative grade points average amongst 2022/2023 final year educational management undergraduate students in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a moderate level.

Hypotheses Testing

The null hypotheses were tested using Linear Regression Analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the following acronym stands as; df = degree of freedom; R = correlation co-efficient and sig = level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between staff working conditions and educational management undergraduate students’ learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

Table 4a: Model Summary of the Correlation between Staff Working Conditions and Educational Management Undergraduate Students’ Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.678 ^a	0.460	0.454	0.836

a. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Working Condition

Table 4a is a model summary that presents the results of the regression analysis examining the correlation between the predictor variable (staff working condition) and the dependent variable (academic achievement). The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is a measure of how well the independent variable(s) (staff working condition) explain the variance in the dependent variable (academic achievement). The results reveal that 45.4% of the variation in academic achievement could be attributed to staff working condition. The results also show that staff working condition has a strong positive correlation with academic achievement as indicated by the r – value of 0.678.

Table 4b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Correlation between Staff Working Condition and Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.987	1	59.987	85.894	0.000 ^b
	Residual	70.537	101	0.698		
	Total	130.524	102			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Working Condition

The results of analysis in Table 4b presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) of linear regression analysis that aims to examine the correlation between staff working condition and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that there is a significant correlation between staff working condition and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, F (1, 101) = 85.894, p < 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4c: Coefficient of the Correlation between Staff Working Condition and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.036	0.234		4.424	0.000
	Staff Working Conditions	0.596	0.064	0.678	9.268	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

The outcome in Table 4c reveals the Beta coefficient derived from the regression analysis assessing the correlation between staff working condition and students’ academic achievement. The constant value (B = 1.036) indicates the starting point or intercept of the model. The coefficient for staff working conditions (B = 0.596) signifies that for every one-unit increase in the staff working conditions variable, the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement) is expected to increase by 0.596 units, assuming all other factors remain constant. This positive coefficient suggests that better staff working conditions are associated with improved students’ academic achievement, reflecting a direct and proportional relationship between the two variables.

Ho2: There is no significant correlation between staff appraisal and educational management undergraduate students’ learning outcome in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria.

Table 5a: Model Summary of Correlation between Staff Appraisal and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.564 ^a	0.318	0.311	0.939

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students’ Academic Achievement

Table 5a shows a model summary that demonstrates how the independent variable accounts for the variance in the dependent variable and the strength of correlation between the variables. The results reveal that 31.1% of the variation in students’ academic achievement could be attributed to staff appraisal. The results reveal that 31.1% of the variation in academic achievement could be attributed to staff appraisal. The results also show that staff appraisal has a strong positive correlation with academic achievement as indicated by the r – value of 0.564.

Table 5b: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression of Correlation between Staff Appraisal and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	41.454	1	41.454	47.007	0.000 ^b
	Residual	89.070	101	0.882		
	Total	130.524	102			

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Staff Appraisal

The results of analysis in Table 5b presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) of linear regression analysis that aims to examine the correlation between staff appraisal and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The result reveals that there is a

significant correlation between staff appraisal and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 47.007, p < 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5c: Coefficients of Correlation between Staff Appraisal and Students’ Academic Achievement in Educational Management Programme

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.121	0.299		3.751	0.000
Staff Appraisal	0.513	0.075	0.564	6.856	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Achievement

The outcome in Table 5c reveals the Beta coefficient derived from the regression analysis assessing the correlation between staff appraisal and students’ academic achievement. The constant value ($B = 1.121$) indicates the starting point or intercept of the model. The coefficient for staff appraisal ($B = 0.513$) signifies that for every one-unit increase in the staff appraisal variable, the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement) is expected to increase by 0.513 units, assuming all other factors remain constant. This positive coefficient suggests that better staff appraisal is associated with improved students’ academic achievement, reflecting a direct and proportional relationship between the two variables.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study found in Table 1 that staff working conditions in educational management undergraduate programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a moderate level, with a grand mean of 3.41. This finding concurred with the findings of Kidanie (2022); Zhenjing, Chupradit, Ku, Nassani and Haffar (2022); and Alyaha and Mbogo (2017) that staff working conditions in tertiary institutions are often at a moderate level. However, the finding disagrees with the finding of Leavic (2021) and Adeniji, Adelena and Ogunbile (2022) findings that staff working conditions are usually at a higher level. The moderate level of staff working conditions indicates that while there might not be severe issues, there is room for improvement. It suggests that there might be some challenges or areas where the working conditions for staff could be enhanced. This could encompass factors such as physical infrastructure, availability of resources, administrative support, and interpersonal dynamics within the department. Improving working conditions could potentially lead to higher job satisfaction among staff, which in turn could positively impact their performance and commitment to the programme.

However, hypothesis 1 was rejected, as the result showed that there is a significant correlation between staff working condition and students’ academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 85.894, p < 0.05$. This finding is in alignment with the studies of Bolarinwa, Onajite, Ogunmilade and Olaoye (2020) that working conditions and salary had influence on teachers’ productivity (students’ success). Also, in agreement was, Kindane (2022) study that revealed that workplace environment factors had positive linear relationship with work place and students’ performance in the university. However, Keston (2015) study found that there is no significant difference between working conditions (such as payment of retirement benefit) and academic staff and students’ performance, which disagrees with the hypothesis finding. The implication of this hypothesis finding is that it reveals that a supportive and conducive work environment for faculty members can lead to improved teaching quality, more effective student engagement, and enhanced learning outcomes. Hence, investing in resources, professional

development opportunities, and support services for staff can contribute to a higher quality educational experience for students, potentially leading to better academic achievement.

The study also found in Table 2 that staff appraisal of Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria is at a high level, with a grand mean of 3.79. This finding thus concurred with Ulabor and Agelebe (2022); Rwothumio, Okaka, Kambaza and Kyomukama (2021); Niyivuga, Otara and Dieudonné (2019) findings that staff appraisal including staff self-evaluation, students– staff evaluation, peer evaluation and evaluation by supervisor, are highly applied at most tertiary institutions. However, Owusu, Kuranchie and Nanyeke (2018) and Davis and Mensah (2020) studies revealed that staff appraisal are moderately conducted while some staff had little knowledge on the objectives for conducting performance appraisal. The implication of the study finding is that it indicates that satisfaction with various aspects of the staff appraisal in educational management undergraduate programme, such as curriculum implementation, publication, conference attendance, teaching strategies, professional development opportunities, and support from colleagues and administration. A positive staff appraisal is crucial for maintaining morale and fostering a conducive work environment.

In addition, hypothesis 2 was rejected, as the result showed that there is a significant correlation between staff appraisal and students' academic achievement in Educational Management Undergraduate Programme in Universities in North-Central and North-East, Nigeria, $F(1, 101) = 47.007, p < 0.05$. Rwothumio, Okaka, Kambaza and Kyomukama (2021) study concurred the hypothesis finding as the results indicated that a moderate positive relationship existed between performance appraisal and academic staff teaching output and students achievements ($r = 0.379, p < 0.01$). However, the finding was in disagreement with Frehun and Tafano (2019) finding which revealed that the lack of validity and reliability of performance appraisal criteria significantly affected teachers' ability to impact effectively. The implication of the hypothesis finding suggests that how faculty members are evaluated and recognized within the program may also impact students' academic performance. Positive staff appraisal practices that recognize and reward faculty excellence can contribute to a higher quality of teaching, more effective student engagement, and improved learning outcomes. Conversely, ineffective or inadequate staff appraisal processes may lead to demotivation among faculty members, potentially impacting their teaching effectiveness and, consequently, student academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that staff working conditions and staff appraisal significantly correlate with students' learning outcome in Universities of North-Central and North-East, Nigeria. The results revealed that effective HRM practices are associated with more positive students' learning outcome. Conducive staff working conditions, fair and transparent performance appraisal systems collectively contribute to creating a supportive and engaging learning environment. This, in turn, fosters positive student attitudes towards the university and enhances academic achievement among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. University administrators should also focus on enhancing staff working conditions, including providing mental health support and reducing stress factors. This improvement can directly contribute to better academic outcomes for students.

2. The university management should align staff appraisal processes with academic goals, encouraging faculty to adopt teaching practices that promote high academic achievement among students.
3. The University Human Resource Management and Academic Affairs Committee should adopt a comprehensive human resource management approach that prioritizes staff support, which will ultimately lead to better academic outcomes for students.

REFERENCES

- Adeniji, A. M., Adelen, O. P. & Ogunbile, Y. O. (2022). Work conditions and staff job commitment: An empirical survey of government-owned Universities. *Management Research Journal*, 11(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.37134/mrj.vol11.1.1.2022>
- Aithal, P. S. & Suresh, K. P. M. (2016). Student performance and learning outcomes in higher education institutions. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 674-684.
- Akpomi, M. E., Tamuno-Omuna, F. & Gbere, R. O. (2021). Influence of working conditions on job performance of business education lecturers in universities In Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 9(4), 71- 78.
- Alyaha, D. O. & Mbogo, R. W. (2017). Impact of working conditions on teacher's job satisfaction and performance in the private primary schools in Yei Town, South Sudan. *IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary*, 8(1), 122-129. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jems.v8.n1.p12>
- Aneth, A. K. (2017). Educational accountability relationships and students' learning outcome in Tanzania's public schools. *SAGE Open* July – September 2017, 1 – 12.
- Arimie, C. J. & Orobosa, A. I. (2023). Employee performance appraisal and career advancement in Nigerian public organizations: An explicatory review. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 254-263.
- Bakari, H. B. & Bambi, B. I. (2021). *Physical and library resource management practices as correlates of educational management students' learning outcome in universities in North Eastern, Nigeria*. A festschrift in Education for Professor Martins Fabunmi, 363 – 381.
- Bakari, H. B. (2019). *Human resource management as correlates of students' learning outcome graduates in business education programme of universities in North Eastern, Nigeria* (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Modibbo Adama University, Yola.
- Bolarinwa, D. A., Onajite, G. O., Ogunmilade, J. O. & Olaoye, A. O. (2020). Working conditions and salary as correlates of teachers' productivity in government-owned secondary schools in Emure Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 6(1), 89-97.
- Dinna, V. & Michal, M. (2015). Performance appraisal and evaluation. In J. D. Wright (ed.). *Encyclopaedia of the Social and Behavioural Sciences*.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN (2013). National Policy on education. Abuja: NERDC Publication.
- Frehun, T. & Tafano, O. L. (2019). Practices and challenges of teachers' performance appraisal in primary schools of Wolaita Zone, South Ethiopia. *International Journal of Current Research*, 11(8), 6906-6924.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P. & Borg, W. R. (2007). *Educational research an introduction* (2nd ed.). Boston, MA: A&B Publications.
- Keston, B. (2015). *Impact of conditions of service on the performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kogi State* (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

- Kidanie, A. A. (2022). Effect of work place environment factors on performance of employees: Empirical study on Wollo University Staffs. *Research Square*, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1560832/v1>
- Korde, B. (2021). *What are learning outcomes? Types, benefits and examples of educational outcomes*. Retrieved online on the 23/11/2021 from <http://www.google.com/amp/s/www.iitms.co.in/blog/learning-outcome-types-benefits-examples/amp.html>
- Leavic, G. M. (2021). Working conditions and performance of tertiary teachers at UM Panabo College. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 5(5), 14-21.
- Muchai, W. H., Makokha, E. N. & Namusonge, G. (2018). Effects of remuneration system on organizational performance of Teachers Service Commission, Kenya. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(11), 132-141.
- Niyivuga, B., Otara, A. & Dieudonné, T. (2019). Monitoring and evaluation practices and academic staff motivation: Implications in higher education within Rwandan context. *SAGE Open*, 1-9. <http://doi:10.1177/2158244019829564>
- Owusu, A. A., Kuranchie, A. & Nanyele, S. (2018). Appraisal practices in pre-tertiary institutions: Evidence from appraisees. *European Journal of Training and Development Studies*, 5(1), 1-13.
- Rwothumio, J., Okaka, W., Kambaza, S. & Kyomukama, E. (2021). Influence of performance appraisal in determining academic staff performance in public universities in Uganda. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(1), 20-32.
- Ulabor, E. A. & Agelebe, I. B. (2022). *Performance appraisal and organizational performance in selected tertiary institutions in Osun State Nigeria*. Retrieved online on 18/5/23 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363994863_Performance_Appraisal_and_Organizational_Performance_in_Selected_Tertiary_Institutions_in_Osun_State_Nigeria
- Usman, R. U. (2015). *Effectiveness of management strategies of school administrators in public and private junior secondary schools of Yola North LGA of Adamawa State* (Unpublished Masters' Thesis). National Open University, Yola Campus, Adamawa State.
- Zhenjing, G., Chupradit, S., Ku, K. Y., Nassani, A. A. & Haffar, M. (2022). Impact of employees' workplace environment on employees' performance: A multi-mediation. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1-13. <http://doi:10.3389/fpubh.2022.890400>